

Towards atom-chip-based magnetic field sensing below the quantum-projection limit

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Integrated atom-chip magnetic field sensor. Laser cooled ^{87}Rb atoms are loaded into a 1D optical lattice which is formed in the slot region of an optical waveguide (left). The optical waveguide is fabricated via electron beam lithography and reactive ion etching from a free-standing Si_3N_4 membrane. (Right) the electric field of the waveguide mode is primarily localized in the slot region, allowing efficient generation of a multi-particle entangled quantum state of atomic spins.

Building on our experimental experience in quantum and classical optics [Volz06*, Hofmann12*, Liebermeister14*, Weber16*, Fischer17*] we aim to develop a new integrated atom-chip sensor which allows magnetic field sensing below the quantum projection limit. The experimental realization of the new sensor will build on two well established key technologies, i.e., (i) laser cooling and trapping of neutral atoms in optical lattices and (ii) micro- and nanofabrication of integrated on-chip waveguide structures [Painter14]. Combining these techniques will establish a completely new integrated atom-chip platform which will enable future applications in quantum metrology and magnetic field sensing with surpassing sensitivity and accuracy.

The major resource for magnetic field sensing below the quantum-projection limit (QPL) are multi-particle entangled quantum states, like spin-squeezed states of atomic ensembles [Sorensen01a, Mitchell10, Vuletic10, Oberthaler14]. Since Sorensen *et al.* pointed out the connection between spin squeezing and entanglement [Sorensen01b], additional classes of multi-particle entangled states like Dicke-states have been identified as new resource for sub-shot-noise phase estimation [Duan14]. E.g. Lewenstein *et al.* report that symmetric Dicke-states in general perform better in metrology applications than anti-symmetric ones [Lewenstein16]. These theoretical findings and ongoing research on the experimental side [Thompson14, Kasevich16] will enable new implementations of magnetic field sensors with better sensitivity.

The central idea of our proposal is to optically couple and entangle the spin degree of freedom of laser-cooled atoms in a 1D optical lattice with the help of a photonic quantum bus [Ciccarello10]. In detail we aim to use the multiple scattering of single photons coupled to a linear array of optically trapped Lambda-type atoms (see Fig. 1, left). Depending on the initial product state of the atomic spins and with the help of post-selection of the transmitted photon polarization different classes of multi-particle entangled spin states can be prepared.

For a successful implementation of this new integrated atom-chip magnetic field sensor several figures of merit have to be taken into account. (i) For the generation of the multi-particle entangled Dicke states of the atomic spins in the optical lattice the respective spin dephasing time T_2^* should be on the order of several 10 μs . This number is a consequence that T_2^* has to be at least 100 times longer than the mean time between two successive photons launched into the waveguide. (ii) The optical coupling parameter β of the radiating atomic dipoles to the waveguide should be as large as possible. To enable the mentioned entanglement protocol [Ciccarello10] a realistic value of $\beta = 0.5$ is a good trade-off against a typical dephasing time $T_2^* = 50 \mu\text{s}$.

To meet all these requirements, as a platform we will focus on an optical lattice of laser-cooled ^{87}Rb atoms coupled to a free-standing slot waveguide. The choice of ^{87}Rb offers the required Lambda-type atomic level structure [Volz06*] combined with the long spin dephasing time of 75 μs [Rosenfeld11*] while the slot geometry promises the required high optical coupling efficiencies [Loncar09]. As first steps into this direction we already demonstrated the evanescent coupling of single quantum emitters to 1D waveguides [Liebermeister14*] and the nano-fabrication of chip waveguides [Weber16*].

Project relevant own publications

- [Volz06*] *Observation of Entanglement between a Single Photon and a Single Trapped Atom*, Jürgen Volz, Markus Weber, Daniel Schlenk, Wenjamin Rosenfeld, Johannes Vrana, Karen Saucke, Christian Kurtsiefer and Harald Weinfurter, Phys. Rev. Lett. **96**, 030404 (2006).
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- [Hofmann12*] *Heralded Entanglement Between Widely Separated Atoms*, Julian Hofmann, Michael Krug, Norbert Ortegel, Lea Gerard, Markus Weber, Wenjamin Rosenfeld, and Harald Weinfurter, Science **337**, 72 (2012).
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- [Weber16*] *Fabrication and optical characterization of long-range surface-plasmon-polariton waveguides in the NIR*, M. Weber et al., arXiv:1607.00224 [physics.optics]

[Fischer17*] *Shifting the phase of a coherent beam with a $^{174}\text{Yb}^+$ ion: influence of the scattering cross section*, M. Fischer, B. Srivathsan, L. Alber, M. Weber, M. Sondermann, and G. Leuchs, *Appl. Phys. B* **123**, 48 (2017).

General References

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- [Oberthaler14] *Scalable Spin Squeezing for Quantum-Enhanced Magnetometry with Bose-Einstein Condensates*, W. Muessel et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **113**, 103004 (2014).
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- [Thompson14] *Reduced spin measurement back-action for a phase sensitivity ten times beyond the standard quantum limit*, *Nature Photonics* **8**, 731(2014).
- [Vuletic10] *Implementation of Cavity Squeezing of a Collective Atomic Spin*, Ian D. Leroux et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **104**, 073602 (2010).